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AWARENESS RAISING & TRAINING PLAN

Schedule dates & topics for D&E webinars and trainings

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Introduction

The present deliverable outlines a schedule of awareness raising webinars addressed to the entire Widening community as well as training webinars addressed to the beneficiaries of the WiderAdvance Facility. The ultimate purpose of these webinars is to advance understanding of the D&E issues as well as to increase capacities of the Widening community, especially of the holders of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) who are beneficiaries of the Academy, namely of the core service of the WiderAdvance Facility.

This deliverable corresponds to Task 2.3 “*Community awareness and training on D&E*” whereby during the lifetime of the project, at least 40 webinars are foreseen which are based on a set of unique topics which will be delivered on a recurrent mode, This holds true especially for the training webinars who are meant to complement the delivery of the Academies, namely the core, individual services package of the WiderAdvance Facility.

The time frame of this deliverable spans until M23, namely November 2026.

The subjects included in the training plan, maybe subject to a slight modification, if contributors of this task, identify important subjects, not currently covered, from the delivery of the first academies and the consultation of NCPs with the prospective clientes of the Facility.

The KPI will be the attendance by 1.000 RTs and RMAs of both types of webinars

Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines separate training schedules for the two typologies of events, namely awareness raising webinars and more in-depth training webinars. Both webinars will be of a two-hour duration including Q&A.

The preliminary list of subjects has largely been developed by following the project's DoA and in addition by the consultation of the partners, based on their experience and the consensus reached among them. The subjects for the **awareness – raising webinars** opt to familiarize the Widening community with broader D&E aspects that are inherent within the EU programmes landscape such as the Open Science, the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Furthermore, they aim to bring to the community's attention D&E as a policy área as well as the instruments available by the EC that help support valorisation of results as well as the networking with key Stakeholders of the holders of key exploitable results (KERs). Last, the Widening community will be inducted into various forms of dissemination, the optimum timing to protect a KER, be introduced to the management of intangible assets as well as introduced to the concept of the continuation of funding instruments mainly consisting of EU and Structural Funds.

The list of **training webinars** has been developed with the main aim to complement directly the customised services of the WiderAdvance Facility, namely the Academies. While the Academies aim at improving the maturity of KERs and strengthen D&E capacities of both Research teams (RTs) and RMAs by empowering more in-depth considerations with the assistance of certain methodologies (Lean Start-Up, Value Proposition Canvas (VPC)), the training webinars address distinct aspects of the valorisation routes of KERs, thus solidifying learning outcomes and D&E capacities.

Online awareness – raising and training events are accessible to the interested RTs and RMAs without the need for a formal application. The latter events can be accessible to the Facility beneficiaries following recommendation of the Key Account Manager (KAM) within the individual service plan per KER.

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List of Acronyms

AW	Awareness raising webinars
DoA	Description of Action
KERs	Key exploitable results
KAM	Key Account Manager
TR	Training webinars
RMAs	Research Managers and Administrators
RTs	Research Teams
VPC	Value Proposition Canvas
STRL	Standards TRL Assessment
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
KICs	Knowledge Innovation Communities

List of Tables

Table 1: Schedule of Awareness Raising webinars				
Year	Webinar nr	Title of webinar	Leading partner – Supporting partner	Observations
Year 1 or 2 within the deliverable time-frame	[number within the series of webinars]	[subjects for familiarisation of the wider public with D&E]	One or two task contributors	Time flexibility and description of the core idea when necessary

Table 2: Schedule of Training Webinars				
Year	Webinar nr	Title of webinar	Leading partner – Supporting partner	Observations
Year 1 or 2 within the deliverable time-frame	[number within the series of webinars]	[subjects for familiarisation of the wider public with D&E]	One or two task contributors	Time flexibility and description of the core idea when necessary

Table 3: Aggregate list of all webinars until M23				
Year	Webinar nr	Title of webinar	Leading partner – Supporting partner	Observations
Year 1 or 2 within the deliverable time-frame	[number within the series of webinars]	[subjects for familiarisation of the wider public with D&E]	One or two task contributors	Time flexibility and description of the core idea when necessary

1. Developing Awareness Raising webinars

Online awareness – raising events open to the entire Widening community, namely RTs and RMAs. To access these webinars, only registration is required (no need for formal application). Beneficiaries of the Facility can attend as well following recommendation by the KAM.

Awareness-raising webinars will be recorded and be deposited at a public section of the Facility's website.

The time span of awareness-raising webinars is M23, namely November 2026. The start date is June 2025 with the end date on October 2026. The times indicated in the schedule are subject to slight modification.

1.1. Awareness raising webinars

For this part of massive online services towards to Widening community, **10 unique subjects** have been identified which progress from more general D&E aspects to more concrete and specific ones. Awareness-raising webinars will start becoming recurrent within the Awareness & Training plan for the period M24-48.

How they were compiled & feedback loops: Based on the DoA and the consensus among partners, especially those who have the function of the NCP and have a basic understanding of their **anticipated** ecosystem's needs. Should consultation with potential beneficiaries of the Facility reveal an important topic not anticipated, the awareness –raising plan will be **adjusted**. Last, the online feedback surveys distributed after each event, will be used a complementary source of feedback.

The awareness-raising subjects address D&E at the EU landscape. They will explain the D&E strategy of the EU, describe the available valorisation instruments and show how they can be used.

Then, D&E will be addressed in terms of the EU-funded programmes in terms of the contractual obligations for D&E as well as in the context of contractualisation of relationships such as within the consortium agreements. Dissemination will be explained through the lens of Open Science and the reproducibility by way of open-access platforms and trusted repositories. Furthermore, within the EU funding landscape, the Widening community will be presented how EU programmes and structural funds could work in synergy for the benefit of maturation of KERs. In this light, interested holders of KERs will be explained how to better utilize the EU brokerage/partnering events in order to expand their collaborative network and pursue more effectively funding opportunities that will help them further mature their KERs.

Last, the Widening community will be inducted into the principles of tech and knowledge transfer, the relationship between dissemination vs protection (exploitation), dissemination to different stakeholders that could lead to bigger chances of exploitation and the general principles of protection of intellectual assets.

Last, but not least, synergies will be sought with the IP Helpdesk for the subject "Introduction to IP protection and management".

Below follows Table 1 with the schedule of awareness-raising webinars.

Year	Webinar nr	Schedule of Awareness Webinars (AW)			
		Title of Awareness Webinar	Leading partner - Supporting partner	Expected month of delivery	Observations
Year 1	1	D&E strategy of the EU. Why D&E is important in EU-funded programmes? Brief intro of the WiderAdvace Facility	FORTH	M5-6	Date includes one month-deviation. We will contact the EC for a speaker to deliver a short presentation
	2	Utilising valorization instruments of the EU	EM - CSIC	M 7-8	Introduction of the the WiderAdvance Facility. Possibly in the Symposium ABRE 2025 "Advances in Biomedical Research": http://abre2025.com
	3	D&E obligations in the Horizon Europe: Articles in Grant Agreements and Consortium Agreements	SIPAC	M 9-10	Date includes one month-deviation
	4	Utilising networking platforms available by the EU	CVTISR, SIPAC	M10-11	Brokerage/partnering events. The times indicated include a deviation by one month
	5	Synergies between EU programmes or between FPs and ESIF funds	CVTISR, FRCT	M11-12	The times indicated include a deviation by one month
Year 2 (until Nov. 26 - M23)	6	Open science & Reproducibility for greater impact	CSIC, CVTISR	M14	Includes EOSC + Open Research Europe
	7	Result dissemination for different stakeholders	EM - APRE	M16	Important consideration especially when projects involve the quadruple helix stakeholders
	8	Knowledge vs Technology Transfer: Similarities and Differences	CSIC	M18	Non-commercial/ non-technical knowledge can be transferred to and hence exploited by different stakeholders
	9	Result dissemination vs protection	CSIC-APRE	M21	Possibly invite an external speaker from an association of universities who have elaborated public statements on open science + IP protection
	10	Introduction to IP protection and management	APRE - EM	M22	Possibly in collaboration with IP Helpdesk

TABLE 1: AWARENESS - RAISING WEBINARS

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2. Developing Training webinars

Training webinars are open to the beneficiaries of the WiderAdvance Facility, following recommendation by the KAM. To access these webinars, no need for formal application; only registration will be needed. Training webinars will be of two-hour duration, or slightly more, including Q&A.

How they were compiled & feedback loops:In consultation with the partners involved in the Academies and the provision of individualised services. The operations manual available to KAMs will contain access to the Training Webinars list. KAMs will be asked to assess during the **engagement meeting** with KER owners if any important training topic is missing. The schedule will be re-assessed after the two cut-off dates of the Facility, namely after January 2026. Last, the online feedback surveys distributed after each event, will be used a complementary source of feedback.

Training webinars will be recurrent majorly in the follow-up deliverable from M24-48. Nevertheless, already two webinars will be recurrent in the Months 22 & 23 regarding Tech Transfer Part 1 and Unitary and unified patents. **Furthermore, recurrent means that the organising partner(s) will repeat the webinars.**

Training webinars will be stored at a dedicated space at the project's website, restricted to the beneficiaries of the WiderAdvance Facility.

The time span of awareness-raising webinars is from M11-23, namely from November 2025 to November 2026. This is justified by the fact that the training webinars need to follow the schedule of the Academies of the Facility. Their scheduling tends to be more "clustered", so that the beneficiaries of the Facility can access these online courses in reasonable proximity to the individualised services. This means that the timing indicated in the table of the training webinars maybe subject to slight modification.

2.1. Training Webinars

The aim of the training webinars is to complement the workshops of the Academy of the WiderAdvance Facility. While the KER owners will be contemplating on the potential of their results and crafting D&E plans, the online courses will acquaint them with the distinct items of the valorisation route, such as:

- **Tech transfer**

- Tech transfer: From Bench to Market: Part 1 – 2
- Transition to Entrepreneurship, ie. when to consider founding a spin-off vs licensing
- IP strategies from HEIs/PROs with use cases
- IP scan, Patent search and databases

- **Protecting Intangible Assets**

- Unitary patent and unified patent. Practical steps for the application

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- EU Trademarks and designs
 - Developing – Implementing technical standards
- Standardisation

In total, **8 unique subjects** will be developed and **2** out of them will be recurrent.

Below follows Table 2 with the schedule of training webinars.

Year	Webinar nr	Schedule of Training Webinars			
		Title of Training Webinar	Leading partner - Supporting partner	Expected month of delivery	Observations
Year 1	1	Tech transfer - From the bench to the market: Part 1	CSIC, UNICO	M11	Industrial Property and Technology Transfer: licensing, recognizing the value of a result (commercial or not), protection, dissemination after protection, licensing vs. creating an EBT
	2	Transition to Entrepreneurship	FORTH	M12-13	Date includes a month-deviation. To be delivered by the Tech Transfer office of FORTH
Year 2 (until Nov 26, M23)	3	Unitary patent and unified patent. Practical steps for the application	UNICO, CVTI SR	M13-14	Date with a possible one- month deviation. Possibly in collaboration with WIPO
	4	IP scan, Patent search and databases	CSIC	M14	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies. Possibly with the help of IP Helpdesk
	5	EU Trademarks and designs	UNICO	M16	Possibly in collaboration with EUIPO
	6	Tech Transfer - From Bench to Market: Part 2	CSIC	M17	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies
	7	IP strategies from HEIs/PROs with use cases	EM	M19	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies
	8	Standardisation	Trust-IT	M21	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies
	9	Recurrent until M23: Tech transfer - From the bench to the market: Part 1	CSIC, UNICO	M22	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies
	10	Recurrent until M23: Unitary patent and unified patent. Practical steps for the application	UNICO, CVTI SR	M23	Tentative date. Depends on the delivery of the academies

Table 2: Training Webinars

3. Summarising webinars (aggregate)

Below follows a table summarising the schedule of both awareness – raising (blue color) and training webinars (green color). The schedule for the next 20 months looks very dense. The only limitation is that some contributors are actively involved in both types of webinars. This requires caution so that there is no conflict in the schedule of specific partners such as IPNA/CSIC, CVTI SR, EM. Therefore, the spacing the precedes the actual start of the delivery of the webinars, provides sufficient time to the partners involved to prepare the webinar content in advance, so that there not major changes in the schedule.

M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23
May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25	Sep-25	Oct-25	Nov-25	Dec-25	Jan-26	Feb-26	Mar-26	Apr-26	May-26	Jun-26	Jul-26	Aug-26	Sep-26	Oct-26	Nov-26
Awareness raising webinars on D & E																		
	D&E Strategy	EU Valorisation instruments		D&E in HE		EU Networking platforms	Synergies EU-ESIF		Open Science		Diss. to different stakeholders		Knowledge vs Tech transfer			Diss. vs protection	Intro to IP Management	
Training webinars to the beneficiaries of the WiderAdvance Facility																		
No Facility beneficiaries yet						Tech Transfer: 1	Trans to entr/ship	Patents and application process	IP scan, Patent search & databases		EU Trademarks & designs	Tech Transfer: Part 2		IP strategies HEIs/PROs: use cases		Stand/tion	Tech Transfer: 1	Patents and application process

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF WEBINARS 1

4. Complementarity of Training Webinars to the methodologies of the WiderAdvace Facility

The Training Webinars have a certain degree of complementarity in relation to the methodologies to be used by the experts during the Academy of the WiderAdvace Facility. More specifically:

- **STRL: The Standards TRL Assessment** (<https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/store/trl-assessment>) would be the first evaluation step. It is important to correctly determine whether a result needs more development before transferring it to other stakeholders, or whether should benefit from developing it jointly with other stakeholders. This topic is addressed in different webinars, particularly: in the Awareness Program, webinars No 9 (Result dissemination vs protection) and No 10 (Introduction to IP protection and management); in the Training Program, webinar No 1 (Tech transfer - From the bench to the market: Part 1), No 2 (Transition to Entrepreneurship), No 6 (Tech Transfer - From Bench to Market: Part 2)
- **Lean Startup approach – VPC: The Lean Startup approach** (<https://theleanstartup.com/principles>) and the **Value Proposition Canvas** (<https://www.strategyzer.com/library/the-value-proposition-canvas>) are much used when designing a company (particularly an EBT) and eventually finding out whether the products/services will be really demanded by the society, and whether adjustments or even pivoting the company's profile should be made. These methodologies are incorporated in different webinars and most notably within those mentioned before.

5. Monitoring & evaluation

The aim is to mirror to the extent possible, the blocking issues mentioned in the **Task 4.6 “Impact monitoring, barriers’ analysis and policy recommendations”**

Monitoring & evaluation will be integral part of the training programme because feedback loops will need to be fed in the services of the WiderAdvace Facility. Moreover, the monitoring – evaluation will help contribute to the assessment of the impact to the **degree concerned** on the service delivery, on improvement of the skills and knowledge as well on barriers and bottlenecks to the D&E.

Monitoring and evaluation will happen through brief online survey forms. The attendees will be asked to respond to few closed-ended question involving rating 1-5 and to a couple of open-ended questions. In respect to the closed-ended questions, they will aim to establish the prior knowledge of attendees of a given subject matter, the extent that they acquired new knowledge items, as well as how important the topic was for their job.

- **Training webinars:** Attendees will be asked to complete the online feedback forms available at the intranet of the Facility's website. **Acceptable response rate: 90%**
- **Awareness raising webinars:** Before the end of the webinars, attendees will be handed a link to the form (tool will be defined). The acceptable response rates are as follows:
 - **up to 100 participants: 20% minimum response rate.**
 - **up to 300 participants: 10% minimum response rate.**

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- >300: below 10%.

6. Dissemination

Dissemination of the **awareness raising webinars and especially the Plan**, will be based on the engagement of the WIDERA NCP Community, **including** through NCP_WIDERA.NET Project (where this is possible), the ambassadors of the Project, the non-WIDERA NCPs through the NCP Networks, the EIT KICKs as well as the Enterprise Europe Network.

As soon as the 1st call of the Facility is announced, more dissemination momentum will be created and events announced through the Facility's website will enjoy more visibility.

On the contrary, training webinars will be disseminated through the KAM to the service beneficiaries, and thus an acceptable attendance rate will need to be determined.

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